

Facilitated transport of copper(II) across chloroform liquid membrane using different carriers

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Manuscript received 30 November 2000, revised 21 March 2001, accepted 26 March 2001

Six different carriers, namely, isobutanol, isopropanol, 2-nitroaniline, benzophenone, methyl methacrylate (MMA) and epichlorohydrine and their effective comparative transport of Cu^{II} across a bulk liquid membrane (BLM) have been successfully studied. The feed comprises of a solution of Cu^{II} of an effluent from electrochemical industries maintained at pH 2, while 0.1 M hydrochloric acid served as a stripping agent in the receiving compartment of the permeation cell. Near about 80% Cu²⁺ permeates across the membrane in less than 4 h through 2-nitroaniline as the carrier whereas the transport of Cu²⁺ is as low as 42% for benzophenone carrier. The initial rate of transport (J_c) of Cu²⁺ for different carriers has also been studied.

Now a days the electrochemical industries play an important role in the commercial world. Under the general umbrella of electrochemical technologies for waste minimization is to recover and removal of valuable components from waste waters¹. Many of the treatment processes are known today. However, the facilitated transport membrane (FTM) is a new and elegant technique for removal of valuable metals from electrochemical wastes. The carrier facilitated transport generally results in an uphill transport and higher selectivity. Many such transport studies on metal ions across the liquid membrane have been well documented^{2,3}. The aim of this work is to investigate the effective extraction of Cu^{II} using different carriers into organic solvent to a membrane process. Recently, the recovery and removal of copper from electrochemical waste has become very important due to its economic value and clean environment. Therefore, the studies on the selection of best carrier and uphill transport of Cu^{II} would be useful for the separation and pre-concentration of the metal ion. In this paper, we have investigated the suitable carrier for effective transport of Cu^{II} from electrochemical effluents.

Results and Discussion

The metal ions get absorbed into the membrane due to the complex formation with carrier at the interface between feed and the membrane. The carrier complex diffuses to the other interface between the membrane and the receiving solution where Cu²⁺ is released into the aqueous phase due to stripping action of the H⁺ ion. The free carrier diffuses back to the interface at the feed side to form complex again with the available fresh Cu²⁺ ions.

The concentration polarization is avoided and their uniform concentration is maintained throughout by con-

tinuous and uniform stirring. The higher acidity of the receiving solution does not permit the recombination of the metal ions with the carrier and prevents the backward transport of copper from the receiving to the feed solution. Thus the difference in the pH of the feed and the receiving solution resulted in the uphill transport of the metal ion.

The pH of the feed solution was greater than that of the receiving solution. The optimum carrier concentration was 1.0×10^{-3} M. Under these conditions, the transport of Cu²⁺ was nearly quantitative. Hence, in all further experiments, the carrier concentration and pH of the feed and stripping solution were maintained accordingly. The variation of the concentration of Cu^{II} in the feed and the receiving solution as function of time, using different carriers, is shown in Fig. 1. It is seen that Cu²⁺ is readily extracted into the organic phase but the permeation sets in slowly. The metal ion is rapidly stripped out into the receiving phase after a time lag and the equilibrium is reached in about 4 h. Table 1 shows the permeation of Cu²⁺ through different carriers.

Table 1. Permeation and transport of Cu²⁺ through different carriers at 4 h duration

Carrier	% Cu permeation	% Cu in feed solution	% Cu in membrane phase	Initial rate of transport $10^4 J_c$, mol h ⁻¹
Isobutanol	46.44	53.43	0.13	7.85
Isopropanol	49.61	49.62	0.77	7.85
2-Nitroaniline	79.51 ^a	19.08	1.41	9.81
Benzophenone	41.35	57.23	1.42	7.13
MMA	67.41	31.79	0.80	13.08
Epichlorohydrine	64.26	34.35	1.39	11.21

^aPermeation of Cu²⁺ through 2-nitroaniline is greater than 99% during 5 h interval.

Fig. 1. Time variation permeation of Cu^{2+} for different carriers : (—) isobutanol, (---) isopropanol, (····) 2-nitroaniline, (—Δ—) benzophenone, (— — —) MMA, (—·—·) epichlorohydrine. Permeation condition : source phase, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M \text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (pH 2.14), receiving phase, $0.1 M \text{HCl}$ (pH 1.48), membrane phase, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ carrier solution in chloroform.

The initial rate of transport of metal ion was very fast. However, with elapsed time, the rate of transport slowed down. This is true for each individual carrier also. It is apparent that as the concentration of the metal ion in the receiving phase increases, the transport of the metal in the reverse direction also sets in, diminishing the net rate of transport of the metal ion from the source phase to the receiving phase. In the present study, therefore, transport data of each carrier have been discussed in terms of initial rates of transport (J_c) which were determined from the tangent at time $t = 0$ in the plots of concentration (in the receiving phase) versus time, t (Fig. not shown).

The initial transport rates (J_c) of Cu^{2+} from the source phase to the receiving phase through the liquid membrane phase for different carriers are recorded in Table 1. A scrutiny of the values of J_c for the same anion (SO_4^{2-}) and the same concentration in the source phase reveals that the carrier, MMA transports the copper ions faster in comparison to the other carriers as follows : $\text{MMA} > \text{epichlorohydrine} > 2\text{-nitroaniline} > \text{isobutanol} \cong \text{isopropanol} > \text{benzophenone}$. It is clear from the above studies that among the six carriers, the 2-nitroaniline can be chosen as a best one for efficient transport of Cu^{2+} because copper metal has the best tendency to form complex with amino compound. MMA and epichlorohydrine considered as monomers also

show better result for transport of Cu^{2+} , in terms of % permeation. The isopropanol, isobutanol and benzophenone which are the alcohols and keto-compound have the tendency to form complex with Cu^{2+} decreased gradually. The overall preference of efficiency of the carriers are : $2\text{-nitroaniline} > \text{MMA} > \text{epichlorohydrine} > \text{isopropanol} > \text{isobutanol} > \text{benzophenone}$.

Experimental

Isobutanol (B.D.H.), isopropanol (B.D.H.), 2-nitroaniline (S. D. Fine Chemicals), benzophenone (S. D. Fine Chemicals), methyl methacrylate (E. Merck) and epichlorohydrine (B.D.H.) were used as such. A $0.01 M$ stock solution of different carriers in chloroform (S. D. Fine Chemicals) was diluted further when required for transport studies.

Feed solution : Synthetic copper ion solution was made from $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H.) as similar to an effluent from electrochemical (Cu-plating) industries and pH was adjusted to 2.

Receiving solution : Hydrochloric acid diluted with deionised water was used as a stripping agent in the receiving compartment of the permeation cell.

Method of transportation : The experimental set up used in the permeation solution has been described elsewhere³. All the transport experiments were carried out at ambient temperature. In a typical experiment, the volumes of the feed and the receiving solutions were maintained at 5 and 10 ml, respectively. The pH of the feed solution was adjusted to 2 while that of the receiving solution to 1 with HCl. All the three phases (two aqueous and one organic) were magnetically stirred with a magnetic bar placed in the organic phase. Copper concentration in the two aqueous phases were determined by iodometric titration.

References

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